

Preparing teachers for the AI Development in Education as an Innovative Asset

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Report on the perception of teachers about the future impact of AI & on teachers' awareness of student perceptions of AI

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20574350

ISBN: 9791298562417

Edited in May 2025

This project has received funding from the European Education and Culture Executive Agency Erasmus Plus Programme Under Grant Agreement no 101132955.

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The PAIDEIA Project is a groundbreaking initiative funded by the European Commission through the European Agency for Education and Culture (EACEA). Our mission is to revolutionize education by integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into teaching and learning, empowering educators, and enhancing student outcomes.

CONSORTIUM

FONDAZIONE HALLGARTEN FRANCHETTI CENTRO STUDI VILLA MONTESCA, an Italian high education research center, coordinates PAIDEIA project. It has been historically founded in 1902 (then institutionally renewed) in the place where the Montessori method was experimented and published for the first time in 1909. It has an international vocation in educative and pedagogic research activities and has a very relevant experience in EU projects management and development. FCSVM has strong partnership with schools and other educational organizations, as well as a solid background in research-actions activities, fostering critical thinking, diversity as a value and innovation from the pedagogical and didactic point of view.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this report is to fulfil the requirements of deliverables D2.2 and D2.4. The report presents combined data on teachers' perceptions about the future impact of AI in education in partner countries, and teachers' awareness of students' perceptions of AI. In doing so, this deliverable informs future project work packages and contributes to the general debate about AI in education. The report is structured in three main sections. Section one outlines the research methodology and approach. Section two presents the findings of the surveys and focus groups, and discusses the implications of these. Section three of the report presents the overall conclusions and recommendations for the project and general implications for AI in education.

2. RESEARCH DESIGN

Following a review of the aims and objectives of the PAIDEIA project, and WP2 in particular, the following themes were identified for investigation in D2.2 and D2.4:

- Current usage of AI in education
- Understanding of AI and how it works, and familiarity with AI and AI tools
- Perceived challenges and threats of AI in education
- Opportunities of AI in education
- Understanding of student perceptions of AI
- Training and CPD for AI in education

To investigate these themes, we adopted an explanatory sequential mixed methodology design, comprising two phases (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). An explanatory sequential design allowed for an in-depth investigation of the themes identified by combining quantitative and qualitative data. The sequential nature of the approach meant that survey data was gathered first, to establish foundational understandings, patterns, and trends. Following this, focus groups were employed to further explore teachers' experiences, perceptions, and understandings.

2.1 SAMPLE AND PROCEDURE

Participants were drawn from the seven PAIDEIA partner countries, namely: Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Italy, Malta, Türkiye, and Spain. Primary and post- primary/secondary teachers in each jurisdiction were invited to take part in the study via a recruitment campaign carried out on various social media channels (E.g. Twitter/X, LinkedIn). Recruitment and distribution of surveys was carried out between May 2024 and July 2024, with a target of 100 respondents per country. Survey participants were invited to express an interest in completing follow up focus groups. Focus group participants were selected based on their willingness to participate, level of experience with AI, and the education level at which they currently teach (primary/post-primary). This ensured a range of perceptions and experience levels. Focus groups were conducted throughout August 2024 and September 2024, with a target of 10 participants per country (5 per focus group). Response rates for the survey in each country were: Belgium: 30; Bulgaria: 100; Ireland: 42; Italy: 100; Malta: 64; Türkiye: 100; Spain: 100. Participation rates for the focus groups in each country were: Belgium: 10; Bulgaria: 10; Ireland: 10; Italy: 10; Malta: 0; Türkiye: 10; Spain: 10. All survey and focus questions were translated by partners into the relevant language.

2.2 RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

As mentioned above, the study adopted two data collection tools: surveys and focus groups. Further details are now provided for each of these instruments.

2.2.1 SURVEYS

While focussing on the themes outlined above, the survey instrument was adapted based on a thorough review of published research and validated questionnaires (Chatterjee & Bhattacharjee, 2020; Ayanwale et al., 2022; Demir & Köklü, 2023; Van den Berg & Du Plessis, 2023; Digital Learning Project, 2019). An initial draft survey was sent to two experts in Dublin City University for feedback. After addressing this feedback, the survey was piloted with 15 teachers. The final version of the survey included a series of predominantly quantitative questions, with some qualitative questions included to gather the thoughts, experiences and perceptions of teachers. Quantitative questions were structured to ascertain participants' level of agreement with a statement by selecting along a five-point scale ('Strongly disagree', 'Disagree', 'Neither disagree nor agree', 'Agree', 'Strongly agree'). Quantitative responses were captured using free text boxes. The themes were addressed using the following questions:

Table 1: Survey themes and questions

Question	Options
General information	
Please select the age range that applies to you	20 – 29 30 – 39 40 – 49 50 – 59 60 -65 65+
Please state the current level you teach at	Primary Post-primary [Options specific to partner country]
CURRENT USAGE OF AI IN EDUCATION	
In your educational practices, are you currently using any Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools to support your teaching or other related activities? If so, please specify the specific tools you utilise (e.g.,	Free text

How often do you use the AI tools you mentioned in the previous question	Never Rarely A few times per term Monthly (1-3 times per month) Weekly (1-3 times per week) Almost Daily
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I use AI tools for planning my teaching curriculum - I use AI tools to enhance student learning experiences - I use AI tools to assess my students - I use AI tools to manage administrative tasks - I use AI to personalise learning for my students - I use AI to analyse educational data - I use AI to assist in providing feedback to students - I use AI to develop interactive and engaging content - I use AI to improve teaching strategies 	Strongly disagree Disagree Neither agree nor disagree Agree Strongly agree
Could you describe a specific instance where AI significantly impacted your teaching, assessment, or administrative tasks?	Free text
What has been the most transformative AI tool you've used in your teaching, and why?	Free text
UNDERSTANDING OF AI	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I understand the basic principles of AI - I am confident in my ability to explain the workings of AI to my students - I believe my current knowledge of AI is sufficient to integrate it into my teaching - I regularly follow updates and developments in the field of educational AI - I understand the ethical implications of using AI in teaching - My school or institution has rules or guidelines on the responsible use of AI tools for assessment - I understand the school or institution's rules or guidelines on the use of AI tools in assessment 	Strongly disagree Disagree Neither agree nor disagree Agree Strongly agree
Can you share an experience where your understanding of AI significantly impacted your teaching approach?	Free text

PERCEIVED CHALLENGES AND THREATS OF AI	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am concerned about the reliability of information produced by AI, including bias - The integration of AI complicates traditional teaching methods - AI may lead to a lack of personal interaction between teachers and students - I worry about data privacy and security issues related to using AI in education - There are insufficient resources available to support effective AI implementation - I am sceptical about the long-term impact of AI on educational equity - I fear AI may devalue the role of the teacher in the classroom 	Strongly disagree Disagree Neither agree nor disagree Agree Strongly agree
What do you consider the biggest challenge in adopting AI in education?	Free text
OPPORTUNITIES OF AI IN EDUCATION	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the future, I think that AI will present opportunities for personalising student learning - In the future, I think that AI will present opportunities for assessment and feedback - In the future, I think that AI will present opportunities for creating innovative teaching materials - In the future, I think that AI will present opportunities for creating innovative teaching methods and approaches - In the future, I think that AI will present opportunities for improving student engagement - In the future, I think that AI will present opportunities for improving access to education 	Strongly disagree Disagree Neither agree nor disagree Agree Strongly agree
What ways might AI be used to improve your students' learning experience?	Free text
What innovative ways do you imagine AI will be used in the future for teaching	Free text

UNDERSTANDING OF STUDENT PERCEPTIONS OF AI	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students are curious about how AI works - Students are generally enthusiastic about using AI tools in learning - Students understand the benefits of AI in their education - Students' express concerns about AI replacing human teachers - Students feel that AI in education enhances their learning experience - Students are concerned about privacy and data security with AI tools - Students trust the feedback and assessments provided by AI - Students are aware of the ethical implications of AI in education - Students see AI as a tool for improving their future career prospects 	<p>Strongly disagree Disagree Neither agree nor disagree Agree Strongly agree</p>
How do students express their views on AI?	Free text
What impact do you think AI has on students' learning and motivation?	Free text
What concerns do students frequently raise about AI in the classroom?	Free text
TRAINING AND CPD FOR AI IN EDUCATION	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I received training that has adequately prepared me to use AI in education - I believe ongoing AI training should be mandatory for educators - There are sufficient opportunities for CPD in AI available to me - I feel confident in seeking out further AI training independently - Professional development in AI has enhanced my teaching effectiveness - I have access to online resources for AI learning and development - What would you like to see included in AI training and professional development programs for educators? 	<p>Strongly disagree Disagree Neither agree nor disagree Agree Strongly agree</p>
What would you like to see included in AI training and professional development programs for educators?	Free text

2.2.2 FOCUS GROUP

Participants were invited to take part in focus groups on Zoom (or alternative online platform). Focus groups lasted between 1 and 1.5 hours and were recorded for later analysis. The focus groups were designed to delve deeper into the themes outlined in the previous section. With that in mind, facilitators were provided with a list of themes and prompts (outlined below). In the interests of consistency across partner countries, facilitators were asked to document key points raised during the focus groups in each theme (during the focus group and by listening back to the recording), plus 2 - 3 meaningful quotes per theme. These points and quotes formed the data that was used for analysis and were documented in English. Table 2 presents the focus group themes and prompts.

Table 2: Focus group themes and prompts

Theme	Prompts
General information	<p>How many participants teach at primary, post-primary, etc. level?</p> <p>How long have participants been teaching?</p> <p>How large is the school or institution? What are the numbers of staff and students?</p>
Understanding of AI	<p>What is your current understanding of artificial intelligence? How would you define artificial intelligence in your own words?</p> <p>Can you describe how AI is currently integrated into the tools or software you use?</p> <p>Are you aware of specific uses of artificial intelligence, where you might encounter AI in your everyday life?</p> <p>Have you heard of Generative or Gen AI?</p> <p>Do you know what this is?</p> <p>Do you know what makes this different from other AI-powered tools?</p>
Use of AI	<p>What AI tools or applications are you currently using in your teaching preparation, design, or delivery?</p> <p>Can you explain to me how you use these?</p> <p>How did you decide to incorporate these AI tools into your practice? What are the advantages and disadvantages?</p>

	<p>Where did you hear about this tool?</p> <p>What AI tools, if any, do you use in your assessment procedures? Can you explain to me how you use these? How did you decide to incorporate these AI tools into your practice? What are the advantages and disadvantages? Where did you hear about this tool?</p> <p>Can you share an example where you used AI in your classroom for something other than teaching preparation, delivery or assessment?</p> <p>In your opinion, is AI having a significant impact on education in your school or institution? What are the common discussion points that arise between you and other teachers or trainers (colleagues)?</p> <p>Are there any AI approaches or practices in education that you are involved in, or that you are aware of that you feel are particularly innovative?</p>
Perceived Challenges and Threats of AI in Education	<p>What are your main fears or concerns about using AI in education?</p> <p>What concerns do you have about the reliability or accuracy of the information it provides?</p> <p>What fears or concerns do you have regarding data privacy or security?</p> <p>What challenges might AI bring to the student-teacher relationship?</p> <p>What concerns do you have about students using AI?</p> <p>Do you believe AI could widen the educational gap between different groups of students? Why or why not?</p>
Opportunities of AI in Education	<p>What opportunities does AI present for education?</p> <p>How might AI be used to improve preparation of teaching materials, teaching delivery, assessment, personalised learning, or student engagement?</p> <p>What innovative teaching methods might be employed in the future, with the help of AI?</p> <p>How do you think AI could help in managing and reducing the workload of teachers?</p>
Students' perceptions of AI	<p>Does the topic of AI in education come up with your students? How do your students generally feel about using AI- based tools for learning?</p> <p>What benefits do students perceive in using AI in their education?</p> <p>Have students expressed any specific fears or concerns about AI?</p>

	<p>What are they?</p> <p>Are your students using AI in their daily lives? In what ways are they using AI?</p> <p>Are your students using AI for their education? In what ways are they using AI for their education?</p>
<p>Training and CPD</p>	<p>How confident do you feel integrating AI into your a) teaching preparation, b) teaching and learning delivery, and c) assessment processes?</p> <p>In your opinion what key knowledge and skills do teachers need to integrate AI into their practice?</p> <p>What training do you require to improve your knowledge and skills in relation to AI?</p> <p>Are you aware of any CPD in relation to AI in education? How is this made available or delivered (e.g. through your school, self-sourced, through a university, etc)? Did you avail of this? What are your thoughts on this CPD?</p> <p>What CPD do you feel is needed that is not currently available?</p>

2.3 DATA ANALYSIS

The data collected was analysed in two ways. Quantitative data was analysed using descriptive analysis. Qualitative data was analysed using thematic analysis (Creswell, 2014). Hsieh and Shannon’s (2005) conventional content analysis approach was employed, where codes were inferred from text answers with the aim of describing the phenomenon. Answers were read, and as categories emerged, answers were given appropriate codes.

2.4 PRESENTATIONS OF FINDINGS

2.4.1 SURVEYS

For each of the themes in the survey, the following presentation strategy has been adopted. Quantitative data is presented in tabular format with each partner country represented, along with a final column which presents the overall data from all partner countries. In an effort to increase the readability and value of the data for future work packages, where appropriate, the report adopts a ‘heatmap’ approach for presenting responses to quantitative data. In these cases, column 1 presents the question posed to participants, columns two to eight present a colour for an individual country, and the final column presents a colour which represents the responses for the overall PAIDEIA countries. The colour code is presented in Table 3 below. Below each ‘heatmap’ table, a summary and comment on the data is presented.

Table 3: Heatmap colour coding

+	Significant majority of responses were 'Strongly agree' or 'Agree'
	Majority of responses were 'Strongly agree' or 'Agree'
+	Significant majority of responses were 'Neither disagree nor agree'
	Majority of responses were 'Neither disagree nor agree'
+	Significant majority of responses were 'Strongly disagree' or 'Disagree'
	Majority of responses were 'Strongly disagree' or 'Disagree'
	No clear majority

In each case, 'significant majority' is defined as a category having 60%+ of responses. 'Majority' is defined as a category having 54%-60% of response, or above 51%, while other categories are significantly lower. For example, a question with 60% 'Strongly agree' or 'Agree', 29% 'Strongly disagree' or 'Disagree', 12% 'Neither disagree nor agree' would be given the colour-code green+. A question with 57% 'Strongly agree' or 'Agree', 20% 'Strongly disagree' or 'Disagree', 23% 'Neither disagree nor agree' would be given the colour-code green. Similarly, a question with 51% 'Strongly agree' or 'Agree', 28% 'Strongly disagree' or 'Disagree', 21% 'Neither disagree nor agree' would be given the colour green. A question with 35% 'Strongly agree' or 'Agree', 43% 'Strongly disagree' or 'Disagree', 22% 'Neither disagree nor agree' would be given the colour blue.

Qualitative data is presented using overall themes that emerged from the data. Qualitative data is presented in narrative form to support and/or develop qualitative data in each theme.

3.FINDINGS

3.1 SURVEY RESULTS

3.1.1.GENERAL INFORMATION

Survey respondents were mainly between 30 and 59 years of age, with those between 40 – 49 years old making up the largest proportion of respondents. A full breakdown of respondents' age profiles is as follows: 20 – 29 years old (8%), 30 – 39 years old (24%), 40 – 49 years old (43%), 50 – 59 years old (20%), 60 – 65 years old (4%), 65 years of age or older (1%). The majority of respondents were teaching at post-primary level (71%), compared to 29% teaching at primary level.

3.1.2.CURRENT USAGE OF AI IN EDUCATION (PLANNING, TEACHING AND LEARNING, AND ASSESSMENT)

In this section of the survey, we asked participants to think about their current use of AI in education. This included areas such as planning, teaching and learning, and assessment.

As can be seen in Figure 1, for those teachers that have used AI in their practice, the most popular tools is ChatGPT. Other tools that feature prominently in responses include CoPilot, Canva, BingAI, and Gemini. Respondents reported a wide variety of lesser-known AI tools that have been included in the 'other' category. Examples of these tools include: Suno AI, Leonardo AI, Eleven Labs, Pop AI, and Magic School AI.

Figure 1: AI tools being used by teachers

Figure 2 displays participants responses to the question: How often do you use the tools mentioned in the previous question? As can be seen, the majority of teachers report non-usage or sporadic usage of AI tools. 36% of teachers say they never use AI, while 17% of teachers say they rarely use AI, and 17% of teachers say they use AI a few times per term. The figures for reported regular AI usage are quite low with 11% of teachers saying they use AI on a monthly basis, 13% stating they use it on a weekly basis, and only 5% saying they use it daily.

As can be seen in the heatmap presented in Table 4, the overall trend for the use of AI across partner countries appears to be mixed to low. Many of the statements received no clear majority in responses, indicating mixed usage. For example, areas such as planning, personalizing learning for students, and using AI to develop engaging content all fell into this category. Other areas indicated that a majority of participants across partner countries are not using AI to support these tasks. These included using AI to assess students, provide feedback, and manage administrative tasks.

Table 4: Current usage of AI in education

	Bel	Bul	Irl	Ita	Mal	Spa	Tür	Overall
I use AI tools for planning my teaching curriculum	+						+	
I use AI tools to enhance student learning experiences	+	+	+				+	
I use AI tools to assess my students	+		+				+	
I use AI tools to manage administrative tasks							+	
I use AI to personalise learning for my students	+						+	
I use AI to analyse educational data	+		+			+	+	
I use AI to assists in providing feedback to students	+		+			+	+	
I use AI to develop interactive and engaging content						+	+	
I use AI to improve teaching strategies							+	

While specific questions yielded results from PAIDEIA countries, some warrant further exploration. For example, using AI to enhance student learning experiences had no clear majority overall. However, a significant majority of teachers in Bulgaria and Ireland indicated they are using AI in this area, while a significant majority of teachers in Belgium and Türkiye indicated they are not. Similarly, while there was no clear majority in responses to using AI to develop interactive and engaging content, a majority of teachers in Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Italy, and Malta say they are using AI to accomplish this. However, this is balanced by a significant majority of teachers in Spain and Türkiye who strongly disagreed with this statement. Areas such as using AI to manage administrative tasks and using AI to analysis educational data received a significant majority of responses which indicated a lack of use in these areas. However, Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Italy, and Malta had a mixed response to this question. Similarly, teachers in Bulgaria appear to be using AI to analyse educational data, while Italian teachers had mixed responses.

The data also reveals some interesting insights on a country-by-country basis. For example, we can see that teachers in countries such as Belgium, Spain and Türkiye display little use of AI overall. However, Bulgaria, Ireland, Italy and Malta have more mixed responses. It appears that they are using AI in certain circumstances, but not in others.

This data shows that AI usage among partner countries is generally mixed to low, with many areas lacking a clear majority of responses. The application of AI to areas such as planning, personalising learning, and creating engaging content had mixed usage, while tasks like assessing students, providing feedback, and managing administrative tasks were mostly not supported by AI. Notable country-specific insights include Bulgaria and Ireland's higher adoption of AI for enhancing

student learning experiences, contrasting with low usage in Belgium and Türkiye. AI usage for developing interactive content also varied, with Spain and Türkiye reporting significantly less usage compared to other countries. Overall, countries like Belgium, Spain, and Türkiye display limited AI use, while Bulgaria, Ireland, Italy, and Malta show more varied adoption patterns.

Could you describe a specific instance where AI significantly impacted your teaching, assessment, or administrative tasks?

Participants were asked to describe a specific instance where AI significantly impacted their teaching, assessment, or administrative tasks. Many responses were either blank or indicated AI was not being used. Table 5 displays the responses that indicated AI was being used and reveals that the overall majority of responses fell into the 'teaching' category, followed by 'assessment' and 'administration'. In Spain, however, the majority of responses fell into the 'assessment' category.

Responses indicated an interesting mix of integration of AI. Responses in the teaching category were spread across four areas: lesson preparation and materials; interactive and creative projects; student engagement; and subject-specific applications. Lesson preparation and materials included the use of AI in the preparation of lecture slides and lesson plans, idea generation for content and exercises, the development of diverse teaching materials such as interactive lessons and images, and the customisation of teaching materials to suit different learning styles and needs. Interactive and creative projects included the use of AI to create animations, illustrated stories, and other multimedia content for projects and other initiatives. It also involved the use of AI for developing creative exercises such as song creation, poster design, and character development. Student engagement involved the use of AI to make lessons more engaging and interactive, and facilitating new ways of student participation such as game-based learning. Subject-specific applications involved the use of AI in subject contexts such as mathematics, science and programming. Responses in the assessment category were spread across three areas: creating and grading assessments; feedback and evaluation; and adaptive learning tools. Creating and grading assessments included the use of AI to generate test questions and assessment criteria, the use of AI-enabled platforms like Kahoot for quick assessments, and the use of AI-assisted grading to identify knowledge gaps. Feedback and evaluation use included using AI to provide personalised feedback, and summarising student performance to improve assessment design. Adaptive learning tools included the use of AI to design adaptive assessments for different levels and creating differentiated tasks for students with special educational needs. Responses in the administrative category were spread across three areas: report and document preparation; data management and analysis; and communication and coordination. Report and documentation preparation includes using AI to create and edit reports, presentations, and administrative documents, and using AI to structure documents such as lesson plans and reports. Data management and analysis activities supported by AI include organisation and analysis of data related to student performance, and preparing data for school reports. Communication and coordination are supported by AI through AI-generated content and using AI to streamline administrative processes.

Country	Teaching	Assessment	Administration
Türkiye	18	6	3
Bulgaria	22	12	5
Belgium	10	8	7
Spain	14	18	3
Ireland	19	5	5
Italy	28	6	3
Malta	19	7	4
Total	130	62	30

Table 5:

Impact of AI

The participants' responses reveal that AI impacts various aspects of their teaching, assessment, and administrative duties. In teaching, AI is used to prepare lesson materials, create interactive and creative projects, and engage students in new ways. For assessment, AI aids in creating and grading assessments, providing personalised feedback, and designing adaptive learning tools. In administrative tasks, AI helps streamline report preparation, manage data, and enhance communication, potentially saving time and improving efficiency.

What has been the most transformative AI tool you've used in your teaching, and why?

Table 6: Transformative AI tools

Country	ChatGPT / LLM	Assessment	Specialised	Creative	Integrated AI	Nonuse
Türkiye	30	4	3		11	78
Bulgaria	35	5	4	10		10
Belgium	11		4	1		14
Spain	19		4	6		22
Ireland	15		6	2		7
Italy	28		4	8		34
Malta	30	7	2	5		12
Total	168	16	27	32	11	165

Participants were asked to state the most transformative AI tool they have used in their teaching, and explain why. As can be seen in Table 6, it must first be noted that many participants

stated that they are not currently using AI. Of those that are using AI, the following information can be gleaned. ChatGPT and other LLMs are the most prominently used tools. Most respondents simply listed the tool. Those that provided reasoning, included factors such as its ease of use, ability to easily create content and questions, and the quality of responses produced. The second category of AI tools being used were creative ones. These included tools such as Canva, Dall-E, Craiyon, which are being used for image generation and editing, video creation, and presentation creation. Teachers are also using specialised AI tool targeted towards specific subject and curricular areas. Tools mentioned include MathGPT, Speechify, and AI maps. Teachers in Türkiye also spoke of applications with integrated AI features such as Microsoft language translation and Diffit. The final category of AI tools being used were related to assessment. These included tools such as Smart Test, Quizziz, and Magic school.

3.1.3. UNDERSTANDING OF AI AND HOW IT WORKS, AND FAMILIARITY WITH AI AND AI TOOLS

In this section of the survey, we asked participants to think about their understanding of AI and how it works.

Table 7: Understanding of AI and how it works

	Bel	Bul	Irl	Ita	Mal	Spa	Tür		Overall
I understand the basic principles of AI	Green	+	+	Blue	Green	Blue	Blue	Black	Green
I am confident in my ability to explain the workings of AI to my students	+	Blue	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Black	Blue
I believe my current knowledge of AI is sufficient to integrate it into my teaching	+	Blue	Blue	Red	Blue	Red	Red	Black	Blue
I regularly follow updates and developments in the field of educational AI	+	Blue	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Black	Blue
I understand the ethical implications of using AI in teaching	Yellow	+	+	+	Green	Green	Blue	Black	Green
My school or institution has rules or guidelines on the responsible use of AI tools for assessment	+	Blue	+	+	Red	+	Red	Black	Red
I understand the school or institution's rules or guidelines on the use of AI tools in assessment	+	Blue	Blue	Red	Blue	Red	Blue	Black	Blue

As can be seen in the heatmap presented in Table 7, overall understanding of AI and how it works across PAIDEIA country participants varies depending on the area. For example, the majority of teachers indicate an understanding of the basic principles of AI and ethical implications of using AI in teaching. In many of the other areas, there appears to be mixed levels of understanding. For example, there was no clear majority of agreement around teachers' confidence in explaining the

workings of AI, keeping up to date on developments in the field of AI, and in having a sufficient level of knowledge to integrate AI. The only area where the majority of teachers disagreed was the availability of guidelines on the responsible use of AI. Overall, participants feel this is not the case.

Certain questions warrant further exploration. For example, while the overall indication was that teachers understand the basic principles of AI, this question received a mixed response from teachers in Italy, Spain, and Türkiye. While overall, there was no clear majority of agreement in terms of sufficient knowledge to integrate AI, a majority of teachers in Italy, Spain, and Türkiye disagreed with this statement. Also notable is that the majority of teachers in Ireland follow updates in the field of AI, in contrast to the overall result of ‘no clear majority’. The area with the most consistent level of disagreement was the availability of guidelines on the responsible use of AI. Notable here is that responses from Bulgarian teachers held no clear majority, while the majority of Belgian teachers neither disagreed or agreed that they were available.

The data also reveals some interesting insights on a country-by-country basis. For example, the majority of Belgian teachers responded ‘neither disagree nor agree’ to most of the questions, indicating perhaps a lack of awareness around these topics or areas. Bulgarian teachers are perhaps the most confident in their understanding, with no statement receiving a majority ‘disagree’. Irish teachers also appear to be relatively confident, with only one statement receiving a significant majority ‘disagree’, while four others received a majority or significant majority agreement. Italian, Maltese, and Spanish teachers have mixed confidence in their understand, with statements receiving mainly no clear majority, and some receiving either a majority agreement or majority disagreement. Türkiye is the only country where no statement received majority agreement from teachers, indicating a lack of confidence in their understanding of AI and how it works.

This data shows that overall understanding of AI among PAIDEIA country participants varies significantly. While most teachers understand the basic principles and ethical implications of AI, confidence is mixed when it comes to explaining how AI works, staying updated on AI developments, and integrating AI effectively. The majority of teachers disagreed about having sufficient guidelines on responsible AI use. Country- specific trends include a lack of confidence among Italian, Maltese, Spanish, and Turkish teachers, while Belgian teachers often responded neutrally, suggesting limited awareness. Bulgarian and Irish teachers appear more confident in their AI knowledge compared to others.

Can you share an experience where your understanding of AI significantly impacted your teaching approach?

Table 8: An experience where your understanding of AI significantly impacted your teaching approach

Country	Enhancing practices & outcomes	Personalised Learning & engagement	Challenges & concerns	Non- use
Türkiye	17	6	2	10
Bulgaria	21	3	3	23
Belgium	8	0	1	4
Spain	14	3	2	27
Ireland	7	3	10	9
Italy	14	7	4	60
Malta	18	10	14	22
Total	99	32	36	155

Participants were asked to share an experience where their understanding of AI significantly impacted their teaching approach. As can be seen in Table 8, it must first be noted that the majority of respondents stated they are not using AI or have too limited experience with AI to comment. Of those that did comment on AI's impact, the following information can be gleaned. The majority of comments related to enhancing educational practices and outcomes. For example, teachers spoke about using AI to create animated visuals, analyse data, create itineraries, and prepare materials. Teachers also spoke about using AI to personalise learning and increase engagement. For example, teachers mentioned developing personalised learning plans, simplifying text for students, automated translation, and finding unique examples. Teachers also spoke about challenges and concerns. For example, they said AI doesn't 'give the information I need', and that it might minimise the teacher's presence. They also highlighted challenges in students' use saying, 'I caught students using AI to do homework' and that 'learners don't understand the material but can appear as though they do'.

It appears that teachers in PAIDEIA countries are beginning to harness AI to enhance teaching, create engaging content, personalise learning, and improve student outcomes. However, concerns

about the misuse of AI, accuracy of AI outputs, and an over-reliance on AI remain. This, coupled with the substantial number of teachers not using AI, points to a need for accessible training and resources to build confidence and competence in integrating AI into teaching.

3.1.4. PERCEIVED CHALLENGES AND THREATS OF AI IN EDUCATION

In this section of the survey, we asked participants to think about the challenges and threats AI poses in education, now and in the future.

Table 9: Perceived challenges and threats of AI in education

	Bel	Bul	Irl	Ita	Mal	Spa	Tür		Over all
I am concerned about the reliability of information produced by AI, including bias	+	+	+	+	+	+			+
The integration of AI complicates traditional teaching methods									
AI may lead to a lack of personal interaction between teachers and students									
I worry about data privacy and security issues related to using AI in education			+	+		+			+
There are insufficient resources available to support effective AI implementation			+						
I am sceptical about the long-term impact of AI on educational equity									
I fear AI may devalue the role of the teacher in the classroom	+								

As can be seen in the heatmap presented in Table 9, overall perceptions of the challenges and threats AI poses in education range from mixed to strong. The reliability of information produced by AI and concerns about data privacy and security issues related to AI come through strongly as challenges or threats perceived by teachers. All other areas received a mixed response, including the impact of AI on personal interaction between teachers and students, the long-term impact of AI on educational equity, and the danger that AI will complicate traditional teaching methods.

Many of the statements received consistency in responses from individual partner countries. However, some warrant further exploration. For example, a significant majority of partner countries strongly agreed that the reliability of information produced by AI is a concern, except for Türkiye, where participants’ responses yielded no clear majority. Similarly, a majority or significant majority of teachers in all partner countries except Bulgaria worry about data privacy and security issues related to AI. Bulgarian teachers had no clear majority in this area. There was no clear majority in the overall

sentiments of teachers from partner countries around the long-term impact of AI on educational equity and the fear that AI may devalue the role of the teacher. However, the majority of teachers in Ireland and Italy were concerned about the impact of AI on educational equity, while a significant majority of teachers in Belgium and a majority of teachers in Bulgaria and Ireland were not concerned that AI might devalue the role of the teacher.

Country-specific responses are remarkably consistent across partner countries, with only minor differences noted. For example, Belgian, Bulgarian and Irish teachers may be seen to be slightly less fearful of the impact of AI, with a majority or significant majority disagreeing with one of the statements (I fear AI may devalue the role of the teacher in the classroom). Teachers in Türkiye may have a slightly more balanced perception of the challenges and threats posed by AI, presenting no clear majority in their responses to all questions, with the exception of one (There are insufficient resources available to support effective AI implementation), where there was a majority agreement.

This data highlights mixed to strong perceptions of the challenges and threats AI poses in education. Key concerns across partner countries include the reliability of AI-generated information and data privacy issues, with most countries agreeing on these points, except for Türkiye and Bulgaria, where no clear majority emerged. Mixed responses were noted on the impact of AI on educational equity, devaluing the teacher's role, and the effect on teacher-student interactions. While countries like Ireland and Italy showed concern for equity, and Belgian, Bulgarian, and Irish teachers expressed less fear about AI devaluing their roles, Turkish teachers exhibited a more balanced view of AI challenges overall, with no clear majority except regarding insufficient resources for AI implementation. Overall, country-specific responses were consistent, with only minor variations.

What do you consider the biggest challenge in adopting AI in education?

In answering this question, teachers commented on concerns about the accuracy and reliability of information produced by AI, with comments such as 'content produced by AI must be verified', 'hallucinations, lack of testing', and 'reliability of information'. Comments also provided further detail on how AI might impact teaching practices and methods, with teachers saying it will be a challenge balancing 'technology use with traditional methods' and that teachers should 'make conscious use of it'. The issue of teaching practices also appeared in comments in relation to assessment, with comments identifying the challenges in 'assessing students' actual learning with AI in the mix', 'identifying plagiarism', and designing 'reliable assessments that measure what has been learned'. In relation to teaching, a fear noted in qualitative findings was the potential for negative impact on student creativity. Comments stated we should 'avoid over-reliance on AI' as it may 'reduce students' desire to build their natural intelligence' and could reduce 'student creativity and critical thinking'. The lack of personal interaction was also elaborated upon in qualitative comments. Comments spoke of the challenge in maintaining the human elements, and social and emotional aspects, with comments such as 'remain human', 'preserve empathy and teacher-student interaction', and 'maintaining the individual need of each child'. Comments also spoke of fears of 'limited exchange of ideas and reflections', and lessening the 'relationship with learners. Data privacy and security concerns were represented in the qualitative data with comments speaking of the 'sensitivity regarding personal information', 'security violations', 'responsible use of AI', and 'data protection'. Resources and equity appeared in a number

In the future, I think that AI will present opportunities for creating innovative teaching methods and approaches	+	+	+	+	+	+	+		+
In the future, I think that AI will present opportunities for improving student engagement	+	+	+		+				
In the future, I think that AI will present opportunities for improving access to education	+				+		+		

As can be seen in the heatmap presented in Table 10, overall perceptions of the opportunities presented by AI for education are remarkably positive. Most statements received a majority or significant majority of ‘agree’ or ‘strongly agree’ responses. Areas that received a significant majority were personalised learning opportunities, opportunities for assessment and feedback, the creation of innovative teaching materials, and the creation of innovative teaching methods and approaches. Areas that received majority were opportunities around improving student engagement and improving access to education.

In terms of individual statements, there was relative consistency in responses from individual partner countries. However, three questions did not receive a consistent majority of ‘agree’ or ‘strongly agree’ in their response. The areas of personalising student learning and opportunities for assessment and feedback received a significant majority of ‘agree’ or ‘strongly agree’ responses. However, in both cases, Italian teachers returned no clear majority in their responses. Opportunities for improving access to education received a majority agreement across PAIDEIA countries. However, Italian teachers returned no clear majority in their responses.

In fact, looking at country-specific responses, there is clearly positive perceptions around the opportunities of AI in education across all areas, with the exception of Italy. Responses from Italian teachers indicate that they are positive about many areas but are unsure about the opportunities AI will provide for personalising student learning, facilitating assessment and feedback, and improving access to education.

This data highlights generally positive perceptions of AI’s potential in education across PAIDEIA countries. Most educators agreed or strongly agreed on the benefits AI offers, particularly in areas like personalised learning, assessment, innovative teaching materials, and methods. While the majority also endorsed AI’s role in enhancing student engagement and access to education, Italian educators were less consistent in their agreement. Notably, they showed reservations about AI’s impact on personalising learning, assessment and feedback, and improving educational access, suggesting some hesitancy about these specific benefits of AI. Overall, despite Italy’s reservations, educators across the PAIDEIA countries appear optimistic about AI’s educational potential.

What ways might AI be used to improve your students' learning experience?

Teachers commented on personalised learning and individualised education, saying AI might be useful in “Creating more personalised learning plans for students” and “Customising the curriculum to the

needs of each learner”. Comments also provided further detail on assessment and feedback opportunities. Comments included “Feedback and analysis can be faster and more individual” and “AI could perhaps automate the assessment process of students by analysing their answers to tasks and tests and providing immediate feedback”. Comments also spoke to AI’s potential role in creating innovative teaching materials and innovative teaching approaches. Teachers said, “AI can support gamified learning platforms that make education more engaging and fun” and AI may be useful in “creating engaging and interactive content” such as “creating visual videos, music lessons, preparing presentations”. They also said that AI could improve “the learning experience” with “with simulations, especially in courses that require practice”. Student engagement also appeared in qualitative comments with teachers saying AI “will keep students’ attention” as it is “is new and interesting for students, which would lead to higher concentration and desire”, the overall sentiment in responses is summed up well by “AI will be able to make the learning process much more varied, even fun”. Access to education was mentioned from a number of perspectives. For example, one teacher said, “access to this tool for the most disadvantaged groups” must be prioritised as it “can be adapted to students’ needs” and has the potential to increase “the inclusion of children with disabilities” and “support the student also through language support”. Qualitative comments also included areas such as: Opportunities that AI might provide in supporting critical thinking and creativity. Comments included “AI stimulates creative thinking, curiosity, and originality in students”, “It acts as a good interlocutor in idea generation”, and that AI provides students the opportunity to practice “critical thinking on information provided”. Improved teacher efficiency. Comments included “It could free up teacher’s time to concentrate on planning and conducting extra-curricular activities” and “I think it will definitely help in the bureaucratic component”. Opportunities for language teaching. Comments included “It is especially effective in learning foreign languages”, “I find it interesting to be able to speak with an AI that simulates being a native speaker of a language to practice oral language”, and “Improved interaction in foreign languages”. Facilitating research and information retrieval. Comments included “It may become easier to conduct research and investigation” and “It can be used to aid students in finding information”. It should be noted that, similar to previous sections, teachers also spoke about challenges in this section. These included the need for teacher training, the importance of ethical use of AI, and promoting responsible use of AI in education.

In this section, teachers highlighted the potential of AI in personalised learning, assessment, and creating innovative teaching materials, emphasising faster feedback, gamified learning, and engaging content. They also noted AI’s potential to enhance inclusion, critical thinking, creativity, language learning, and teacher efficiency.

What innovative ways do you imagine AI will be used in the future for teaching?

Qualitative comments in this section centred around the use of AI for personalised learning, increased engagement and motivation, and idea generation and administrative tasks. Teachers commented that AI will be able to tailor experiences and resources to meet students’ unique needs. This was particularly relevant for individualised assessments. They said AI will create “Individual lesson plans, individual assessment and evaluation” and AI could be used as “a personal mentor/tutor to students who are falling behind or who have advanced”. Their comments also suggest AI could be used to increase engagement and motivation through innovative experiences and materials.

Comments included “It can be used to make topics interesting and to convey information to children who are addicted to screens” and “AI will be an integral assistant, through videos, presentations, tasks, and games that will provoke students to have fun while learning”. Teachers also feel that AI will become an invaluable support in terms of idea generation and administrative tasks. Comments included “suggesting tasks that save teacher time”, “Creating lesson outlines”, and “Facilitating the most monotonous tasks, so that time can be dedicated to more creative tasks”. Similar to previous sections, teachers also raised ethical concerns, which comments like “AI means the end of human education” and “I fear that they will lack the critical capacity that only a plurality of teachers can generate”.

3.1.6. UNDERSTANDING OF STUDENT PERCEPTIONS OF AI

In this section of the survey, we asked participants to think about their students’ understanding of AI, based on their experience and interaction with them.

Table 11: Understanding of student perceptions of AI

	Bel	Bul	Irl	Ita	Mal	Spa	Tür		Overall
Students are curious about how AI works	+	+	+	+	+	+	+		+
Students are generally enthusiastic about using AI tools in learning	+		+	+	+				
Students understand the benefits of AI in their education									
Students’ express concerns about AI replacing human teachers	+	+	+						
Students feel that AI in education enhances their learning experience	+								
Students are concerned about privacy and data security with AI tools	+		+		+				
Students trust the feedback and assessments provided by AI				+	+				
Students are aware of the ethical implications of AI in education	+		+	+	+				
Students see AI as a tool for improving their future career prospects									

As can be seen in the heatmap presented in Table 11, students’ perceptions of AI appear to be mixed, with no clear majority of agreement with most statements, and majority agreement and significant majority agreement with one statement. The majority of teachers across PAIDEIA countries perceive their students to be curious about AI and enthusiastic about using AI tools in learning. However,

teachers' understanding of students' perceptions in all other areas are less consistent. For example, areas such as students' understanding of the benefits of AI in their education, students' perception that AI enhances their learning experience, and students' perceptions of AI as a tool for improving future career prospects, all received no clear majority of agreement.

Certain questions warrant further exploration. While there was majority agreement that students are enthusiastic about using AI tools in learning, responses in both Bulgaria and Spain were mixed, returning no clear majority. There were mixed perceptions around concerns about AI replacing human teachers. However, this comprised of varying levels of agreement from individual partner countries. For example, a significant majority of teachers in Belgium and Ireland disagreed, a majority of teachers in Italy and Spain disagreed, but a significant majority of teachers in Bulgaria agreed. Similarly, while there was no clear majority overall in terms of students' concerns about privacy and data security, a majority of teachers from Bulgaria, Ireland and Italy disagreed with this statement. Finally, overall there was no clear consensus on students' awareness of the ethical implications of AI, there was significant levels of disagreement with this statement from Belgian, Irish, Bulgarian, and Spanish teachers, indicating that students in these jurisdictions are not aware of the ethical implications of AI.

The data also reveals some interesting insights on a country-by-country basis. For example, Belgian, Irish, Italian, and Spanish teachers answered more negatively overall than other countries, indicated that teachers in these countries feel students' perceptions around AI are more negative. Conversely, responses from teachers in Malta and Türkiye indicate that, while mixed, students' perceptions around are more positive.

This data suggests that students' perceptions of AI across PAIDEIA countries are mixed, with no strong majority agreement across most statements. Teachers perceive students as generally curious and enthusiastic about AI, yet they find student views on AI's educational benefits, its enhancement of learning, and its role in career prospects to be less clear. Differences emerge on specific issues, such as AI potentially replacing human teachers: teachers in Belgium and Ireland largely disagreed, while those in Bulgaria showed significant agreement. Opinions also varied on privacy and data security, with majorities in Bulgaria, Ireland, and Italy disagreeing about students' concerns.

Furthermore, no consensus was found on students' awareness of AI's ethical implications, with teachers in Belgium, Ireland, Bulgaria, and Spain indicating low awareness among students. Country-specific insights reveal more negative perceptions of AI in Belgium, Ireland, Italy, and Spain, whereas Malta and Türkiye showed a more positive outlook among students.

How do students express their views on AI?

Teachers' responses to how students express their views on AI reveal several recurring themes. These range from enthusiasm and curiosity to misuse and lack of critical awareness. Students see AI as a tool for convenience, saying they often use it to complete assignments and reduce their workload. Many students focus on AI's ability to simplify their academic tasks rather than engaging critically with it. Teachers commented: "They mainly find it an easy tool that takes over work for them, but do not think enough about the answers provided by AI" and "They use it to cancel their commitments, so

they are happy with its existence, and less often to learn something new or generate ideas." AI is seen as a shortcut for learning, where students use AI passively rather than as a tool to deepen understanding. Some teachers noted: "They are enthusiastic because it does their homework" and "They use it mechanically, expressing little interest." Curiosity and enthusiasm towards AI also emerged as a theme, with students expressing excitement about AI's potential. Students seem to view AI as a fascinating new technology with limitless possibilities, often without critically analysing its drawbacks. Teachers said: "They think it's cool, fun, ask Bing crazy questions" and "Students are enthusiastic and ready to use it more often in their learning activities." Despite this enthusiasm, students' lack of critical thinking when using AI is a notable concern. Many teachers reported that students often trust AI-generated content without questioning its accuracy. This is particularly problematic when students use AI for assignments without verifying the information. Teachers remarked: "They think AI is infallible, trust it implicitly and misuse it" and "They are not critical enough with their use and the information they receive." Over-reliance on AI is a potential concern as students sometimes view it as a replacement for their own efforts. Teachers indicated that students often fail to recognise the need to cross-check AI outputs, relying on it as a source of easy answers. For instance: "We don't have to be able to do that anymore, that's what we have AI for" and "They use translators and AI for homework but then copy and paste without checking."

Teachers also commented on a range of diverse opinions and attitudes towards AI. While some students are highly enthusiastic, others are more sceptical or hesitant to use AI. Teachers reported: "Some are quite enthusiastic, others are careful when using it" and "Some use it, others are still sceptical." Conversations and classroom discussions also provide insights into how students express their views on AI. Many students discuss AI in lessons, showing varying levels of awareness and understanding. Teachers commented: "We often discuss new developments and possible concerns" and "They gave me their opinions during the lesson. 9 out of 10 thought it had added value." Finally, teachers spoke of students' limited awareness of AI's ethical implications, highlighting a lack of understanding about the broader consequences of using AI in education. Teachers noted that students are rarely aware of issues like plagiarism or the potential negative effects on their learning: "There is no expression of their views. The student sees that they can get it to do work for them, but have no concept that it is unethical and harms their learning" and "Students are enthusiastic and at the same time few criticisms or awareness of its dangers even before its potential."

In summary, teachers' responses indicate that students express a range of views on AI, from curiosity and enthusiasm to over-reliance and uncritical use. While some students embrace AI as a convenient tool, others use it without fully understanding its limitations or ethical implications. These themes suggest a need for increased education on the critical use of AI to ensure students are using it to enhance learning rather than bypassing valuable educational processes.

What impact do you think AI has on students' learning and motivation?

Several themes regarding the positive and negative effects of AI on students' learning processes and motivation levels are evident. Decreased Motivation and Learning: A significant concern voiced by many teachers is that AI may decrease students' motivation and engagement in the learning process. Students may become over-reliant on AI, leading to reduced effort in learning tasks. Teachers fear

that students are using AI as a shortcut, which diminishes their intrinsic motivation and perseverance. Examples include: “It lessens it as I have received essays created by AI. It is an easy way out for them and adds nothing to their learning” and “AI reduces students' motivation... They use it for ease and do not question whether the answers generated are correct or not.” Over-reliance on AI: Many teachers expressed concerns that students are becoming too dependent on AI, which leads to superficial learning. Students tend to use AI to complete assignments quickly without critically engaging with the content or understanding it deeply. This trend could lead to a decrease in cognitive skills like problem-solving and creativity. For instance: “They often rely on it too much” and “They produce work that is beyond their standard of English. They submit it anyway and make no effort to hide that they used AI.” Increased Curiosity and Motivation: On the positive side, some teachers reported that AI can increase student motivation, particularly due to the novelty and innovation of the technology, e.g. “AI can inspire curiosity, which can lead students to engage more actively with certain subjects.” Teachers who see AI as a motivating tool believe it can spark students' interest in learning, especially in technology-driven contexts. Examples include: “Innovations always arouse excitement for them. While the new world is being shaped through artificial intelligence, insisting on staying away from it will cause regression” and “AI increases the enthusiasm of children who are interested in technology to work.”

Personalised Learning and Increased Engagement: AI's potential to create personalised learning experiences was frequently highlighted. Teachers noted that AI could adapt content to individual students' needs, thereby improving engagement and learning outcomes. This individualised support can benefit students who struggle with traditional teaching methods. Teachers said: “AI can create customized learning experiences by adapting content and teaching methods to the individual needs of students” and “It motivates them to investigate topics further, but students can also use it to complete work for them instead of doing it themselves.” Risks of Intellectual Laziness: Several teachers warned that AI could foster laziness and reduce the cognitive effort students put into learning. By providing quick answers, AI may undermine students' ability to develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills. This intellectual complacency is viewed as a long-term risk to their educational development. For example: “They are not motivated, they use it for ease and do not question whether the answers generated are correct” and “I think it can make learning worse since many times the objective is not to learn but to obtain the maximum benefit with the minimum effort.” Improved Accessibility and Learning Efficiency: Some teachers see AI as a positive tool that can enhance learning by improving access to information and making learning processes more efficient. Students can quickly find information and solutions, which can speed up their learning and make it easier to engage with complex topics. Teachers shared: “AI will facilitate homework, reduce cognitive load. Translated: we will train imbeciles” and “It is a motivating tool for them. It can also make it easier for them to study using different tools, especially for the older ones.”

In conclusion, teachers have mixed views on the impact of AI on students' learning and motivation. While some highlight AI's potential for increased engagement and personalised learning, others are concerned that over-reliance on AI will decrease students' motivation, critical thinking, and effort.

What concerns do students frequently raise about AI in the classroom?

The responses to the question “What concerns do students frequently raise about AI in the classroom?” reveal several key themes regarding students' anxieties and uncertainties about the use

of AI in their learning environments. **Privacy and Data Security Concerns:** Many students are worried about how their personal data might be used or compromised when interacting with AI tools. Concerns about privacy violations are commonly raised, particularly around data protection. For example: “Students are concerned about privacy and data security when using AI tools” and “They express how they can be sure that they have accessed real information, and that a fictional truth may have been created.” **Job Security and Future Employment:** A recurring concern is the potential impact of AI on job markets, with students fearing that AI might replace human jobs, making certain professions obsolete in the future. Students express anxieties about whether their future careers are secure in an AI-dominated world. Responses include: “They are concerned that if not used correctly it may cause more harm than good” and “They talk about future unemployment.” **Credibility and Accuracy of AI-generated Information:** Another concern is about the reliability of AI-generated information. Some students question whether they can trust the output provided by AI, especially with potential inaccuracies and biases. For example: “Some worry that the information received is not adequate and is incomplete or inaccurate” and “The credibility of the information.” **Ethical Issues and Misuse of AI:** Students also raise concerns about the ethical use of AI, including worries about plagiarism and whether using AI might hinder their learning by reducing the effort required to complete tasks. Responses indicate that students are grappling with the potential ethical implications of AI. Examples include: “The main concerns were whether the use of AI is a type of plagiarism” and “Total plagiarism and non- questioning of quality and content.” **AI Replacing Human Interaction:** Several students express concern that AI could diminish personal interactions, including their relationships with teachers. They fear that AI might replace the role of educators and reduce the human element of learning. Some students also worry about losing the personal touch and emotional connection that comes with human teachers. Example responses include: “They fear that there is no more dialogue with the teacher” and “Students fear that AI can replace the teacher.” **No Significant Concerns or Awareness:** Interestingly, many teachers reported that their students either did not raise any concerns about AI or were not yet aware of its potential risks and challenges. Some students view AI as a convenient tool without fully understanding its broader implications. Examples of this theme include: “They don't express concerns” and “I have no such comments. I have been implementing AI work relatively recently.” **Concerns about AI's Limitations:** A few students express concerns about AI's limitations, particularly its inability to understand context, humour, or nuances in human communication. They also worry that AI may not be able to replicate the interactive, engaging teaching style they value in human teachers. For example: “They can't leave the evaluation part, they think they will make mistakes. I get feedback such as the explanation of the subject will not be interactive, our jokes will not be understood, and we will feel very dull.”

In summary, while some students are concerned about data privacy, job security, the credibility of information, and ethical issues, many have yet to express significant concerns. Those who do express apprehensions tend to focus on the potential for AI to replace human jobs or interactions, the reliability of AI-generated content, and the broader ethical implications of using AI in education. However, many students remain enthusiastic or unaware of the potential risks associated with AI.

3.1.7. TRAINING AND CPD FOR AI IN EDUCATION

In this section of the survey, we asked participants to think about existing training and CPD provision for AI, and their needs in this regard.

Table 12: Training and CPD for AI in education

	Bel	Bul	Irl	Ita	Mal	Spa	Tür		Overall
I received training that has adequately prepared me to use AI in education	+		+	+			+		
I believe ongoing AI training should be mandatory for educators	+		+		+				
There are sufficient opportunities for CPD in AI available to me			+						
I feel confident in seeking out further AI training independently			+						
Professional development in AI has enhanced my teaching effectiveness									
I have access to online resources for AI learning and development			+						

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As can be seen in the heatmap presented in Table 12, teachers' responses to training and CPD for AI in education were predominantly mixed, with only one area of majority agreement and one area of majority disagreement. Overall, teachers in PAIDEIA countries feel that AI training should be mandatory for educators and that there is not adequate training provision currently. However, there is less agreement on whether sufficient CPD opportunities currently exist, their confidence in seeking out training, and access to online resources for AI learning and development.

Certain questions warrant further exploration. The majority of teachers feel that AI training should be mandatory, however, there was no clear agreement on this question from teachers in Spain and Türkiye. The majority of teachers feel they have not been provided with adequate training, however, there was no clear agreement on this issue from teachers in Bulgaria. Many of the areas which received no clear majority overall, had strong levels of agreement or disagreement within individual partner countries. For example, a significant majority of teachers in Ireland, and a majority of teachers in Italy

disagreed that sufficient CPD opportunities are available to them. Confidence in seeking out further training opportunities received no clear consensus across PAIDEIA countries, however, a significant majority of teachers in Ireland, and a majority of teachers in Bulgaria and Malta express confidence in this regard. Finally, while access to online resources for AI learning and development appears to be inconsistent across PAIDEIA countries, a significant majority of teachers in Ireland, and a majority of teachers in Bulgaria, feel they have access to these resources.

The data also reveals some interesting insights on a country-by-country basis. Bulgarian teachers appear to be the most positive in relation to training and CPD for AI in education, with no areas of disagreement and four areas of agreement. Maltese teachers also have predominately positive views on training and CPD for AI in education, with only one area of disagreement, two areas of agreement, and remainder having no clear majority. Belgian, Spanish, and Turkish teachers each have only one area of disagreement (having received adequate training on AI in education), with all other areas being positive or mixed. Irish and Italian teachers appear to have the most mixed views, with a range of disagreement, no clear majority, and agreement across the statements.

This data reveals that teachers' responses regarding training and CPD for AI in education are mostly mixed, with only one area of majority agreement and one of majority disagreement. Teachers across PAIDEIA countries largely agree that AI training should be mandatory and feel there is insufficient training provision. However, views are divided on the adequacy of CPD opportunities, confidence in seeking further training, and access to online AI resources. Notably, teachers in Spain and Türkiye showed no consensus on mandatory training, and those in Bulgaria had mixed opinions on the adequacy of training provision. In individual countries, strong opinions emerged: a significant majority in Ireland and a majority in Italy feel that CPD opportunities are lacking, while teachers in Ireland, Bulgaria, and Malta are confident in seeking training. Additionally, teachers in Ireland and Bulgaria generally feel they have access to online resources, though access is inconsistent overall across PAIDEIA countries. Country-specific insights show that Bulgarian and Maltese teachers tend to have positive views on AI training and CPD, while Irish and Italian teachers have more mixed responses, with a balance of agreement, disagreement, and no clear consensus across statements.

What would you like to see included in AI training and professional development programs for educators?

Qualitative data spanned a number of interconnected areas. Teachers would like practical training which shows them how to integrate AI into their teaching. They spoke about “practical examples, things I can implement every day” and “how to use AI effectively and how to put it into practice”. They also mentioned subject-specific training that was tailored to their specialist area. Specific subjects mentioned included science and language learning. In addition to information about using AI for teaching, teachers are interested in learning how AI can help streamline administrative tasks, reducing their workload and allowing them to focus more on teaching. Comments included: “Use of AI software to streamline the administrative and bureaucratic component of teaching work”. On a broader level, teachers expressed the need for foundational knowledge about AI, including its history and function. They also seek training on how to handle data privacy, misuse, and the ethical implications of AI. Teachers value interactive training formats such as workshops and collaborative sessions where they can share best practices, learn from each other, and engage in hands-on activities. Given the rapid advancements in AI, teachers stress the importance of ongoing training that stays

current with new developments and updates in AI technologies. Comments included “Further training (courses will quickly become outdated)” and “Ongoing CPD and refresher courses”. Finally, teachers request access to user-friendly AI tools and resources that can be easily integrated into classroom activities. They prefer tools that are practical, free or affordable, and come with clear instructions. Comments include “Handy, user-friendly tools that can be applied within classroom practice” and “suggested uses based on case studies”.

3.1.8 SUMMARY OF SURVEY DATA

The survey data indicates that AI usage in education among PAIDEIA partner countries is generally low to mixed, with significant variation in how and where AI is applied. AI is sporadically used for tasks like lesson planning, personalizing learning, and content creation, while areas such as assessment, feedback, and administrative tasks see even less support through AI tools. Countries like Bulgaria and Ireland show higher adoption of AI to enhance learning experiences, whereas usage in Belgium, Spain, and Türkiye remains minimal. Understanding of AI among teachers also varies widely; while most teachers grasp basic AI principles and ethical considerations, many lack confidence in explaining AI processes, staying current with advancements, and applying AI effectively in educational settings. Teachers across PAIDEIA countries identify challenges such as the reliability of AI-generated information and data privacy issues, with mixed views on whether AI might undermine educational equity, diminish the teacher’s role, or impact teacher-student dynamics. Despite these concerns, educators are generally optimistic about AI’s potential to personalize learning, innovate teaching methods, and engage students, though Italian teachers expressed some hesitancy around these benefits. Teachers’ perceptions of students’ views on AI reveal mixed enthusiasm and awareness, with students generally seen as curious but unclear about AI’s benefits and potential ethical issues. Country-specific insights show that student perceptions tend to be more positive in Malta and Türkiye, while more negative in Belgium, Ireland, Italy, and Spain. Lastly, there is broad agreement on the need for mandatory AI training for teachers, with insufficient training provisions noted across countries. Opinions are mixed regarding the adequacy of CPD opportunities, confidence in pursuing further training, and access to online AI resources. Teachers in Ireland and Bulgaria generally feel they can access these resources, whereas other countries report inconsistency. Bulgarian and Maltese teachers tend to view AI training and CPD positively, while Irish and Italian teachers express more mixed opinions. Overall, the findings highlight a need for structured, accessible training on AI in education, with a strong emphasis on practical applications, ethical considerations, and tailored CPD resources to build teacher confidence and capacity for AI integration.

3.2 FOCUS GROUP RESULTS

3.2.1 BELGIUM

Participants in the Belgian focus groups had experience ranging from one to 28 years, and worked in schools which ranged in size from 70 pupils to 3000 pupils. Teachers understanding of how AI works is relatively limited as they have limited experience using the technology. They understand the difference between AI and generative AI, stating that AI uses large language models to produce new

texts based on data. They also understand that AI can be used to generate fake videos and images. Much of their knowledge and experience arises from hearing about AI in general conversation, rather than in the context of education. Some teachers are not using AI in education at all. Those that are using it, use it for a variety of tasks such as creating multiple choice questions, analysing, correcting, and providing feedback on student texts, and creating personalised assessments. One teacher commented that “AI does relieve some of my duties” and can be an “inspiration for new lessons”. The perceived challenges and threats posed by AI in education were described by teachers along a number of lines. Some teachers noted that students are not crucial enough and that they may blindly trust AI and become overly reliant on it. This is typified by this statement by one teacher: “It is already very difficult for pupils to know the difference between fake and relevant information. AI makes it even more difficult for them. It scares me”. Others spoke of the need to rethink homework and assessments with the threat of plagiarism and the need to ensure creative thinking is developed. Also mentioned was the fear of some students being left behind either due to a lack of knowledge on how to use AI or due to a lack of access to AI. Opportunities of AI in education expressed by teachers included opportunities for non-native newcomer children and their families, where AI can translate in-class material for students and school documents for parents. AI is also seen as a potential support for students where it can aid in reading material, check students’ work, and make recommendations for improvement. Finally, teachers saw opportunities for differentiation and personalisation where AI can provide differentiated lessons based on student competency level, and personalised feedback. For example, a teacher said: “for children who need extra challenges, I think that could be a useful tool”. Student Perceptions of AI were relatively limited. Teachers expressed the view that students are aware of AI and are already using it to support their learning, however, they are often unaware of how AI works and the impact it may have on their learning. For example, one teacher said, “they sometimes don’t seem to notice that blind trust in AI also takes away their own learning opportunities”. One teacher also expressed students’ unease with the integration of ChatGPT, stating it changes the traditional learning dynamic, which students find uncomfortable. They said, “The students are not always happy, rather surprised when they know that we are going to use ChatGPT together in class. They know that working with language and ChatGPT can be quite intensive and that I don’t ask them to do simple input-output exercises”. Training and CPD for AI in education responses indicate that teachers are willing to learn about AI in education but that opportunities have been limited in this regard to date. Teachers emphasised the importance to peer learning and knowledge exchange on the use of AI, also advocating for teacher-leaders who could champion the use of AI and share their expertise with others.

3.2.2 BULGARIA

Participants in the Bulgarian focus group had experience ranging from five to 34 years, working mostly in large schools. Teachers understanding of how AI works appears to be mixed with primary teachers possessing a limited understanding of AI and post- primary teachers expressing greater confidence in understanding how AI works. Their use of AI in education appears across a range of areas, with primary teachers using AI to generate ideas, create content, create questions and lesson scenarios. However, primary teachers are reluctant to involve students in the use of AI. Post-primary teachers in the focus group are actively using AI, working with students to generate ideas and analyse data. The perceived challenges and threats posed by AI in education expressed by primary teachers were

general in nature, uncertain of the impact on education, especially in the early years of schooling. Post-primary teachers are concerned about the impact of AI on teacher and student autonomy, reliability of data, and the role critical thinking will play in the use of AI. All teachers in the focus groups saw opportunities of AI in education in terms of personalising tasks, analysing errors, and adapting materials for students. They also see value in AI for creating scenarios and assessments. Post-primary teachers see opportunities in creating pedagogical strategies, data analysis, and automating assessments. Students' perceptions of AI at primary level indicate that they are using AI for homework tasks. However, teachers are concerned that students do not understand what AI does and do not verify the information provided. Post-primary teachers feel that students are adapting and starting to use AI for education purposes. However, they fear that students do not always understand the potential risks. Training and CPD for AI in education responses indicate that teachers are eager to learn more and want access to more resources. They express the need for a deeper understanding of how AI works and how it can be integrated into educational materials.

3.2.3 IRELAND

Participants in the Irish focus groups had experience ranging from one year to 30 years and worked in schools which ranged in size from 65 to 600 pupils. Teachers' understanding of how AI works was limited, with participants being familiar with some terms and recognising recommendation systems on their favourite apps such as Netflix. Beyond this, teachers were relatively unclear about aspects such as what makes GenAI different. Participants speaking of using AI in education in a limited way. ChatGPT is being used for translation, administrative tasks, and assisting students with additional needs. There was a recognition that AI is becoming more prevalent in education and teachers may need to engage with it more. Teachers said: "The only tool I use is ChatGPT but I'd use it for admin stuff like letters or communication" and "If you were to come back and have this conversation this time next year there would be a lot more, because it's starting. People are starting to experiment". Teachers raised several challenges and threats they fear may be posed by AI in education. These ranged from data privacy and the ethical use of AI to the trustworthiness of information produced by AI and the misuse of this information in academic contexts. Teachers also noted the danger that AI may widen the socio-economic gap between students from different backgrounds. Teachers' comments include: "There's huge biases. There's misinformation. There's disinformation" and "you do wonder about ... in terms of data protection, ethical implications. If people are putting things into ChatGPT or other platforms". Opportunities of AI in education included the potential to narrow the gap for children with Special Educational Needs and for whom English is not their first language. AI also offers opportunities for differentiation and personalisation of learning. It also holds potential for innovative assessment practices. Teachers' comments included: "From a special [education] perspective, there's a lot of positives there in terms of what AI can do to bridge the gap in learning". Student perceptions of AI include its potential to assist with homework, however they are aware that it may not be an honest approach. Most students do not fully understand what AI is and how it works and have limited experience using it either at home or in education. Teachers' comments ranged from "On the whole [AI] never comes up, and I'd be surprised if the majority of them knew what it was at all" to "The curiosity is there for sure." Training and CPD for AI in education responses indicated that there is a real need for provision in this area. Many teachers do not feel confident in their ability to use AI effectively. Teachers felt that CPD should focus on a small number of effective tools that

have been approved for use at a national level. Teachers' comments included: "Teachers need to be trained in the use of AI, the benefits, the pitfalls, and also then to be able to extend that, to be able to work with students to show what it can and can't do, and the drawbacks of it" and "I do think the Department will have to provide guidance".

3.2.4 ITALY

Participants in the Italian focus groups had experience ranging from ten to 24 years and worked in schools which ranged in size from 154 to 1400 pupils. Teachers' understanding of how AI works was fair to average. Teachers are aware of the existence of AI and have some understanding of how AI works. However, they are not as confident in using AI, while appreciate its potential value in the future. Teachers displayed limited use of AI in education. Some experimented with using AI to generate questions and quizzes for their students. However, there is little opportunity to discuss its potential with colleagues in school. In fact, some teachers said there is resistance to the use of AI in schools, especially among older teachers. Perceived challenges and threats expressed by Italian teachers included the potential negative impact on student intellect and creativity, the homogenisation of answers – where AI presents bland responses that are not responsive to specific cultures or settings, negative impact on the role of the teachers, lack of empathy in AI responses, and the erosion of human responses in classrooms. Italian teachers identified various opportunities of AI in education. These included the potential for AI to support students with additional needs and differing abilities, image generation, lesson preparation, and personalisation of lessons. Teachers also highlighted specific examples, such as using AI to 'chat' with texts in English or bringing the past to life by 'talking' to historical figures. Students' perceptions of AI indicate it is not an area of great concern. Students are only aware of AI to a low degree, and predominately see it as a tool for use in their personal lives rather than education. They do not see AI as a tool that will replace teachers or traditional education approaches. Teachers have received little training or CPD for AI in education. They would appreciate input in this regard. However, they feel training should be provided by other practitioners and focus on hands-on, practical scenarios and use cases so that they can successfully use AI in their teaching and learning.

3.2.5 MALTA

Participants in the Maltese focus groups had experience ranging from ten to 26 years and worked in schools that ranged in size from 250 to over 500 pupils. Maltese teachers understand artificial intelligence (AI) as technology designed to replicate human thought processes. They see AI as a tool that provides ideas, generates content, and aids in solving problems, but its limitations and risks are also acknowledged. For example, one participant said, "It's technology created by humans to replicate cognitive processes, but it's not always accurate and can sometimes fabricate information." Participants were somewhat familiar with Generative AI, identifying it as a tool that creates content such as text and images, based on algorithms and datasets. E.g. "ChatGPT, for example, is a generative AI that helps in doing certain tasks that require more time for humans to do." Participants reported using AI tools to assist with lesson planning, quizzes, and idea generation, helping streamline teaching processes. Responses included: "For preparation, I usually use ChatGPT. Maybe if I'm doing lesson plans worksheets and I get stuck I turn to ChatGPT for ideas", and "I used AI to create a video on

network models, comparing client- server networks to fast food restaurants and peer-to-peer to picnics, helping students grasp the concept quickly.” Maltese teachers are concerned about over-reliance on AI, its impact on creativity, and ethical challenges like plagiarism. They fear AI might reduce students’ and teachers’ engagement in critical thinking and personal input. Comments included: “My main fear is that I’m becoming less creative because I’m relying on AI. It’s like using a calculator—you get the answer, but you lose the mental process”, and “Sometimes we do not take enough into consideration the fact that at a young age, the children’s working memory is still developing.” Teachers believe that AI presents significant opportunities to enhance education by improving efficiency, personalizing learning, and engaging students in innovative ways. Examples include lesson planning, feedback automation, content organisation, streamlined tasks. Some teachers comments include: “Sometimes I’m stuck on how to make a topic more interesting. AI helps by suggesting ideas or creating visuals for presentations”, and “I haven’t used it for grading yet, but I imagine it could save time in providing feedback on written work.” Teachers commented that students frequently engage in discussions about AI tools, reflecting their interest in using technology to enhance learning, with comments such as, “They were excited. It’s something innovative, something that’s really new. They obviously enjoyed using it.” However, stuents also express concerns: “They do worry because they are using AI in an unhealthy manner. Sometimes students are becoming lazy, relying too much on it.” Confidence in integrating AI into teaching preparation varies. Teachers feel more confident using AI for lesson planning but are less confident about its application in real-time teaching and assessment due to limited experience and training. Comments included: “I feel confident using AI to create posters or enhance presentations, but when it comes to assessments, I haven’t explored it much, so I’m not sure how to go about it”, and “I think my skills are limited, especially when it comes to using AI during lessons or assessments. It’s something I need to explore further.”

3.2.6 SPAIN

Participants in the Spanish focus groups had experience ranging from 12 to 42 years and worked in schools which ranged in size from 100 to 1800 pupils. Teachers in Spain had a broad awareness of what AI is and a limited understanding of how AI works, however their experience with it outside of personal use was relatively limited. They expressed a need to understand it more in the future. Many participants were not using AI in education due to constraints around time, expertise, curriculum overload, and preference for face-to-face teaching. Those that are using it, are using it for tasks such as, preparation, games, and flipped classroom activities. Many of the teachers acknowledged that AI may play a greater role in the classroom in the future. Teachers’ comments included: “Chat GPT has read 1,000 books on the subject. I’ve read maybe 10” and “I’m at that point too. I need to jump into AI”. Challenges and threats raised by teachers include: erosion of students reading, writing, verbal communication, and emotional intelligence; quality and validity of information provided by AI; students ability to spot incorrect information; and the impact on homework and assessment tasks. Comments include: “Kids have to read, write, express emotions. How can AI help here?”, “AI has prejudices” and “We have to use AI not let AI use us”. Opportunities of AI in education mentioned by teachers included: personalised and adaptive learning, reduced administrative burden, and variation of teaching approaches. However, teachers’ comments in this area were somewhat cautionary in nature. They included: “AI will never replace teachers” and “Students must see AI as a tool, as a means, not an end”. Students’ perceptions of AI indicate that they currently see AI as an easy way

out, a shortcut. They do not fear AI and are comfortable using it. They are not concerned with the accuracy of information provided by AI. Comments included: “AI is their big brother who does their homework for them” and “They’re digital natives. They have no fear”. Teachers indicated that Training and CPD for AI in education was relatively non-existent at present, most of the learning they have done has been self-directed. They feel they need training in this area, and that it should be hands-on and practical in nature. Comments included: “AI is their big brother who does their homework for them” and “It changes so quickly, it’s impossible for anyone to train you”.

3.2.7 TÜRKİYE

Participants in the Turkish focus groups had experience ranging from four years to 18 years and worked in schools which ranged in size from 450 to 1100 pupils. Teachers had a general understanding of how AI works and the range of applications and contexts where it is currently being used. They acknowledged the transformational potential of the technology in different fields and its usefulness in our day-to-day lives. Comments included “It is the future that can help us anywhere” and “A new innovation that will affect our lives in the future”. Participants spoke of challenges in using AI in education due to a lack of support and resources available to them. Those who are using AI are primarily using it to help with lesson preparation and editing documents. Comments included: “ChatGPT is an important tool for English; it can correct grammar issues. We also use it in debate classes” and “Public institutions seem a bit hesitant about using ChatGPT and DeepL. They need to support us more. We’re trying to educate children, but it’s important to feel that support behind us. If we had more specific support, we could offer even more opportunities to our students”. Teachers raised several challenges and threats that AI might bring. These included the reliability of information provided by AI, ethical and responsible use of AI, students’ overreliance on AI and the negative impact this might have on their independent thinking, reduction in students’ creative capabilities, and disruption of the relationship between teachers and students. Comments included: “When I assign homework, I want students to do it themselves. They should go through certain cognitive processes to complete their education, which creates a pathway for that learning” and “Sometimes, AI just gets things wrong. It might sound convincing, but it can give completely incorrect answers, which is risky in an educational setting where students might take it at face value”. Opportunities of AI in education included the potential to save time and enhance teaching efficiency, generate quizzes and tailored questions, create individualised education plans, support innovative reading and writing activities, and generate visual content. Comments included: “I find AI very helpful in creating individualized education plans and reading and writing activities for my students” and “AI helps me a lot in creating new questions, saving me a lot of time. It can accomplish tasks in a much shorter period than I normally would, which is very beneficial”. Student perceptions of AI were varied. Some students are actively using AI to generate ideas, generate images, and complete assignments. Others lacked an understanding of AI and knowledge of how to use it. Some students perceive AI as a magical tool capable of answering questions and solving problems, others stick to traditional methods of learning. Comments included: “My students seem to think of AI as a magical computer that can answer any question and solve all problems effortlessly. They view it as something magical”, “Some of my students think of it as something like Photoshop because they primarily use it to create visuals” and “I feel that they are starting to seek the information they need, but it’s important that they combine their own ideas to create something nice”. There is interest among educators for Training and CPD for AI in

education to enhance their understanding of AI for educational purposes. Teachers want to improve their skills and believe that CPD should be offered by institutions and become part of Initial Teacher Education programmes. Comments included: “I don't think we are effective enough in this area. To provide students with the necessary information on a topic, teachers must first develop themselves well, and this development is crucial” and “AI education should be included in teacher training programs at universities, so newly appointed teachers can benefit from this knowledge as well”.

3.2.8.SUMMARY OF FOCUS GROUP DATA

3.2.8.1 *Understanding of how AI works*

The understanding of AI among teachers varied across the focus groups, with distinct levels of awareness and familiarity with the technology. In Belgium, teachers demonstrated a relatively limited understanding of AI, largely due to minimal firsthand experience with the technology. Belgian teachers were aware of AI's ability to create fake videos and images, though much of their knowledge stemmed from general discussions rather than educational applications. In Bulgaria, comprehension of AI differed significantly between primary and post-primary teachers. While primary teachers exhibited a limited understanding of AI, their post-primary counterparts expressed greater confidence in grasping how AI operates. Irish teachers shared a limited understanding, with familiarity primarily in terms like recommendation systems used in popular apps like Netflix. However, they were unclear about the specific features that distinguish generative AI from other forms, reflecting an overall limited depth of understanding. Italian teachers displayed an average understanding, recognizing the existence and basic functioning of AI but expressing limited confidence in actively using it. They saw potential value in AI for the future, though they remained somewhat cautious in their enthusiasm for its application in education. Teachers in Spain had a general awareness of AI and an acknowledgment of its basic functions, though their experience was largely limited to personal use. They expressed a strong interest in learning more about AI, recognizing the growing importance of understanding this technology. In Türkiye, teachers demonstrated a general understanding of AI's functionalities and applications, including its impact across various fields. They acknowledged AI's potential as a transformative force and were enthusiastic about its role in future advancements. This diverse landscape of AI understanding highlighted a mix of curiosity, cautious optimism, and varying degrees of familiarity across different educational contexts.

3.2.8.2 *Use of AI in education*

Teachers' use of AI in education varied significantly across countries, with both enthusiasm and challenges shaping their experiences. In Belgium, some teachers were not using AI at all, while others integrated it for tasks like creating multiple-choice questions, analysing and correcting student texts, and providing personalised feedback. They appreciated AI's potential to lighten their workload and inspire lesson planning, with one teacher noting how AI relieved certain duties and sparked ideas for new lessons. In Bulgaria, primary teachers used AI primarily for generating ideas, creating content, and designing questions and lesson scenarios, yet they hesitated to involve students directly in using AI. In contrast, post-primary teachers actively collaborated with students on AI projects, such as data analysis and ideation, showing a broader acceptance of AI at higher educational levels. In Ireland, AI's

role in education was minimal but emerging, with ChatGPT being utilised mainly for administrative tasks, translation, and supporting students with additional needs. Irish teachers acknowledged that AI is gaining traction in education, anticipating that engagement with it would increase significantly in the coming years. Comments from teachers reflected a budding interest, with one noting they were currently experimenting with AI and expected more widespread adoption soon. Italian teachers had limited AI usage, occasionally employing it to create quizzes and questions but facing resistance to the technology, especially from older staff members. Opportunities to discuss AI's potential in schools were scarce, and a sense of reluctance permeated discussions about its classroom use. In Spain, many teachers refrained from using AI due to time constraints, lack of expertise, and curriculum demands. Those who did use it applied it to preparation, interactive games, and flipped classroom activities. Despite limited adoption, some Spanish teachers saw potential in AI, recognizing that it could play a more prominent role in education in the future. In Türkiye, teachers expressed difficulties in adopting AI due to limited institutional support and resources. For those integrating it, AI proved helpful for lesson preparation, document editing, and language corrections, particularly in English grammar. Teachers valued tools like ChatGPT but felt hesitant public institutions were holding them back from fully embracing AI in the classroom. One teacher voiced the need for support, emphasizing how additional backing could enhance their ability to offer students more AI-driven learning opportunities. Across these countries, teachers were navigating a spectrum of adoption and barriers, with differing levels of comfort, resources, and institutional encouragement shaping how AI is incorporated into educational practices.

3.2.8.3 Challenges and threats

Teachers shared diverse concerns regarding the challenges and threats that AI may pose in education. In Belgium, teachers expressed anxiety over students becoming overly reliant on AI, with some fearing that students might lack discernment and trust AI without questioning its validity. One teacher noted that distinguishing between real and fake information is already difficult for students, and AI could exacerbate this problem. Concerns were also raised about the need to rethink homework and assessments to address potential plagiarism and ensure that creative thinking remains central to education. Teachers feared that students might be left behind if they lack the knowledge or resources to access AI, leading to a divide in student capabilities. In Bulgaria, primary teachers voiced more general, tentative concerns about AI's impact, particularly for young students, while post-primary teachers highlighted specific issues such as the potential impact of AI on both teacher and student autonomy. They were also wary of data reliability and emphasised the importance of fostering critical thinking alongside AI use in classrooms. Irish teachers identified a broad range of ethical and practical concerns, particularly regarding data privacy and the ethical implications of using AI in educational settings. They worried about the biases and misinformation that AI could introduce, along with the socio-economic disparities AI might amplify among students from different backgrounds, and emphasised the importance of data protection and ethical considerations when using AI tools like ChatGPT. Italian teachers feared AI might negatively impact student creativity and intellectual development, concerned that AI-generated responses could lack cultural relevance and specificity. The teachers also voiced apprehension over the potential erosion of their role, as well as AI's inability to convey empathy, which they consider vital in classroom interactions. They worried that AI could result in homogenized answers and reduce the quality of student engagement and original thinking. In

Spain, teachers raised concerns about AI diminishing students' foundational skills, such as reading, writing, verbal communication, and emotional intelligence. They questioned the quality and accuracy of information generated by AI, stressing the importance of helping students identify inaccuracies. They believe that AI could not replace essential human interactions. They were also cautious about allowing AI to influence educational priorities. In Türkiye, teachers highlighted challenges due to insufficient support and resources for integrating AI into education. Those using AI found it helpful for preparing lessons and editing documents, particularly in language learning. However, they noted the lack of institutional backing, with one teacher emphasizing the need for support to better leverage AI in ways that could benefit students. The call for support reflected a broader desire to utilise AI more effectively while mitigating potential drawbacks. Across these countries, teachers expressed a mix of ethical, practical, and pedagogical concerns about AI's role in education, reflecting both the promise and the perceived risks of integrating AI into classrooms.

3.2.8.4 Opportunities of AI in education

Teachers across the focus groups saw AI as a tool with significant potential to enhance various aspects of education, offering both practical and innovative opportunities. In Belgium, teachers highlighted AI's capacity to support non-native newcomer children and their families by translating in-class materials and school communications. This, they noted, could help bridge language barriers for students and parents. They also viewed AI as a valuable resource for assisting students in reading materials, checking their work, and providing tailored feedback to support their learning.

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3.2.8.5 Student perceptions of AI

Across the countries, students' perceptions of AI in education ranged from curiosity to caution, with varying levels of understanding and reliance on the technology. In Belgium, teachers observed that while students are aware of AI and sometimes use it to support their learning, they lack a clear understanding of how AI works or the impact it may have on their educational development. Teachers expressed concerns that students' "blind trust" in AI could detract from their own learning opportunities. One teacher noted that students often feel uneasy with AI in class, especially with tools like ChatGPT, which introduce a dynamic shift from traditional learning, requiring more intensive engagement than simple input-output tasks. In Bulgaria, students frequently use AI for homework but do so without verifying the information, a trend that concerns teachers who fear students' limited comprehension of AI's potential risks. Students are beginning to integrate AI into their educational routines, though their understanding of AI's broader implications remains superficial. In Ireland, teachers reported that while students recognise AI's potential to assist with assignments, they are aware that relying on it might not be the most honest approach. The majority of Irish students have

limited experience with AI and only a basic understanding of what it entails. Teachers observed a general curiosity among students about AI, though it is seldom discussed extensively. Italian students, on the other hand, appear largely indifferent to AI's role in education, viewing it primarily as a tool for personal use rather than a transformative educational aid. They do not express concerns about AI replacing teachers or altering traditional learning methods, instead seeing AI as supplementary to their everyday routines. Spanish students are comfortable with AI, often viewing it as a convenient shortcut rather than a robust learning tool. Teachers noticed that students tend to accept AI's responses without scrutinising the information's accuracy. To some, AI is akin to a "big brother" that completes tasks for them, and their familiarity with technology fosters a certain ease and confidence in using AI. In Türkiye, students displayed mixed perceptions of AI. Some students actively use AI to generate ideas, create images, and complete assignments, perceiving it as a powerful resource. For many, however, AI still holds an almost "magical" allure—a computer capable of solving any problem effortlessly. Some students see AI similarly to Photoshop, using it primarily for visual content creation, while others maintain traditional learning methods and feel sceptical about AI's role in education. Teachers noted that Turkish students are beginning to seek out information through AI, but they emphasised the need for students to combine this information with their own ideas for meaningful learning. Overall, students' perceptions of AI reflect a complex blend of curiosity, dependence, and caution. While they are generally open to AI's potential in education, most lack a deep understanding of its workings or implications, with perspectives shaped by cultural attitudes, educational exposure, and individual experiences with technology.

3.2.8.6 Training and CPD

Across the various focus groups, teachers expressed a strong interest in receiving training and CPD on AI in education, although opportunities for such development have been limited thus far. In Belgium, teachers showed a willingness to learn about AI, stressing the importance of peer learning and knowledge exchange. They suggested that having leaders who could champion AI and share their expertise would be valuable, highlighting the role of collaborative learning in fostering AI integration. Bulgarian teachers voiced eagerness to deepen their understanding of AI and access more resources for integrating AI into their teaching. They emphasised a need for comprehensive resources to better grasp AI's workings and its educational applications. In Ireland, teachers expressed a clear need for structured CPD in AI, feeling underprepared and lacking confidence in effectively using the technology. They called for training focused on a few select tools that have been nationally approved. Irish teachers highlighted the importance of understanding both the benefits and limitations of AI, noting that guidance from the Department of Education would be essential to support educators in this area. Italian teachers also indicated a desire for AI training, though they have received minimal input on the topic. They advocated for practical, hands-on training led by experienced practitioners. Such training, they believe, would equip them with the skills to incorporate AI effectively into their teaching. In Spain, teachers noted that formal AI training is almost non-existent, with most of their learning being self-directed. They felt that hands-on, practical training was crucial, as the fast-evolving nature of AI makes it difficult for anyone to stay fully trained without continuous, adaptive learning opportunities. Turkish teachers also expressed strong interest in CPD to enhance their knowledge of AI for educational purposes. They felt that AI education should be institutionalised, becoming part of both professional development and Initial Teacher Education programs. This, they believe, would equip new teachers with a foundational understanding of AI, allowing them to confidently guide students in

its use. Overall, teachers across these countries shared a common desire for structured, practical training that would empower them to integrate AI effectively into their classrooms. They underscored the importance of institutional support, hands-on learning, and guidance from experienced practitioners, reflecting a collective commitment to developing AI competencies that benefit both educators and students.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The data from both the survey and focus groups illustrate a complex landscape regarding AI use, understanding, and perceptions among teachers in PAIDEIA countries. AI integration in education is generally low, with some countries like Bulgaria and Ireland showing moderate adoption, particularly for enhancing student learning experiences. Teachers have a basic understanding of AI principles but lack confidence in explaining how AI works, staying current with AI advancements, and understanding AI's full implications in educational settings. Concerns around AI's reliability, data privacy, and potential impact on educational equity and teacher roles are prominent. Teachers are optimistic about AI's potential, particularly for personalised learning, but hold reservations about its broader impact on creativity, critical thinking, and teacher-student interactions. Students, on the other hand, display curiosity and eagerness toward AI but often lack a deep understanding, with varied reliance on AI tools without fully grasping their limitations or ethical implications.

Training and CPD opportunities are perceived as inadequate across PAIDEIA countries, with teachers expressing a strong need for structured, practical AI training. This training should focus on both foundational AI principles and practical classroom applications. Teachers are also keen on institutional support, hands-on resources, and guidance from experienced practitioners. This diverse data reflects a growing recognition of AI's potential in education but underscores the need for comprehensive training and a balanced, thoughtful approach to AI integration in classrooms.

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Develop core AI literacy modules: Cover foundational modules that include:

- Interactive materials for educators that explain AI principles, capabilities, and limitations
- Modules on critical thinking to identify biases or inaccuracies in AI outputs
- Tutorials for students showcasing responsible AI use in daily life and education.

Including these modules should address the gaps in confidence and understanding across PAIDEIA countries and provide foundational guidelines for AI use in education.

Create practical application modules for classroom use: Develop curriculum modules enabling teachers to integrate AI into educational tasks such as planning, personalised learning, and assessments. Suggestions include:

- Theory to practice - to ensure practical application, training should include tools and resources for critically assessing AI tools and addressing real- world challenges

- Case studies on subject-specific AI applications (e.g., mathematics, languages, and science)
- Practical guides for tailoring AI tools to various age groups and education levels
- Pilot tests in real-world classroom settings to demonstrate AI's effectiveness.

Include training on AI challenges and ethical considerations: Given teachers' concerns about AI's impact on educational equity, creativity, and teacher-student dynamics, curriculum modules should address these challenges. Include content on fostering critical thinking, discerning AI reliability, and mitigating potential biases. Scenario-based training could help teachers develop strategies for balancing AI's benefits with potential drawbacks. Suggestions include:

- Incorporate real-world ethical scenarios – develop modules featuring real-world examples of AI failures, such as biased algorithms in decision-making or misinformation spread by generative AI. Include exercises where teachers analyse these scenarios, discuss their implications, and propose actionable solutions to mitigate similar risks in education
- Focus on equity and accessibility - highlight how AI can either bridge or widen gaps in educational access, particularly for underrepresented groups. Facilitate discussions on leveraging AI to ensure fair resource distribution and prevent algorithmic biases
- Promote data literacy - include training on how AI processes and uses data, with a focus on data privacy, security, and informed consent. Provide hands-on sessions where teachers evaluate the reliability of AI-generated outputs and learn best practices for managing sensitive student data
- Highlight human-AI collaboration - design modules that emphasize the synergy between AI tools and human creativity in education. Offer case studies illustrating how AI can enhance, rather than replace, teachers' expertise, building trust and acceptance of AI technology
- Scenario-Based training exercises - conduct interactive workshops that simulate challenges, such as managing biased AI grading systems or addressing students overly reliant on AI for assignments. These exercises will prepare teachers to navigate ethical dilemmas and technical issues effectively
- Introduce an AI ethics checklist - provide teachers with a practical checklist to evaluate AI tools before implementation. The checklist should include questions such as: Is the tool transparent about its data sources? Can it be used equitably across diverse student populations? Does it offer avenues for teacher control and oversight?
- Collaborate with ethical experts - partner with organizations or specialists in AI ethics to deliver expert-led training sessions. Include panel discussions and Q&A sessions to address teachers' specific concerns about the ethical implications of AI in education.

Provide structured CPD pathways and institutional support: To accommodate the evolving nature of AI, CPD pathways should be dynamic and tiered, offering opportunities for teachers at all experience levels. Resources should include online modules, peer-learning networks, and mentorship opportunities to foster collaboration. Pilot programs can help refine strategies for AI integration, and

regular updates will ensure the CPD content remains current. Institutional support through dedicated AI coordinators and centralized hubs will further align AI adoption with national education goals and teacher needs.

Promote student-focused AI curriculum awareness: To promote students' understanding of AI, modules should go beyond theoretical knowledge and include practical activities, critical thinking exercises and discussion of ethical implications. Educators should guide students to evaluate AI outcomes in terms of bias and reliability, understand privacy, and explore the societal impact of AI. Activities such as student-led projects, collaborative problem solving, and real-world applications will ensure that students not only understand AI concepts, but also use them responsibly. Key areas of focus include:

- Integrate AI education into existing curricula
- Focus on critical thinking and evaluation
- Highlight ethical and societal implications
- Promote student-Led projects
- Introduce data privacy and security awareness
- Foster collaborative learning
- Leverage real-world applications
- Encourage long-term AI literacy

Tailor content to country-specific needs and adoption levels: Curriculum content should be adaptable to the technological readiness and cultural context of each country. For nations with limited AI infrastructure, the focus should be on basic AI literacy using simple tools and offline materials. Countries with moderate AI deployment may benefit from modules emphasising practical applications, such as leveraging AI for personalised learning. Advanced adopters should explore cutting-edge topics like machine learning and ethical dilemmas in AI.

To ensure relevance and accessibility, it is critical to include translations, local examples, and alignment with national education goals. Key strategies for successful localisation and adoption include:

- Conducting local research - identify specific needs and challenges faced by teachers and students through surveys and consultations
- Develop multilingual resources - ensure accessibility for schools in diverse cultural and socio-economic contexts by translating materials into local languages
- Adapt to technological readiness and infrastructure - provide region- appropriate solutions, such as offline materials for areas with limited internet, and training to maximize the use of available technology. Training programs should include offline resources that can be downloaded and used without connectivity. Teachers should also receive training on effectively utilising available technologies

- Language and cultural barriers - in multicultural countries like Belgium, where students speak multiple languages, training materials should be translated and adapted for different linguistic groups. For example, AI tools for automatic translation, such as Google Translate or DeepL, can facilitate access to content
- Pedagogical traditions and approaches - in countries where traditional educational approaches dominate, teachers may require more guidance on integrating AI without undermining classical methods like discussions and interactive teaching. Programs could include examples demonstrating how AI complements, rather than replaces, these methods
- Socio-economic inequalities - in certain countries, disparities in access to AI technologies between wealthier and poorer regions may necessitate targeted interventions. Training programs can include cost-effective alternatives, like free or open-source AI tools, to ensure equitable access
- Differences in cultural and ethical values – in countries where traditional values influence education, programs should emphasise the ethical use of AI and its alignment with cultural and social values, ensuring AI integration supports, rather than disrupts, societal norms
- Focus on specific subjects – in jurisdictions with particular curricular targets, programs can highlight AI tools designed for specific subjects and use cases. For examples, if language learning is a priority, AI tools for translation and conversation, may be most relevant.

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